

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight A440

1 March 1996

Methane Profile Experiment

For more information contact:

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FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A440

DATE: 113196

Take off :

Landing :

Aircraft Scientist : H. YUCHEN

Flight Leader : I. POSE

Others : J. KENT

D. TIDDMAN

A. WATE

W. PICKERING

Captain : C. O. FOWEN

Co-pilot : M. POSE

Navigator : E. HEATON

Engineer : K. QUICK

Loadmaster : J. LAW

+ A BUTTERWORTH + G. MORGAN

Trials Instructions : WRF 5

Operating area : Southern North Sea

General synoptic situation

TIME :

103402

T/O Boscombe Darn

112453(13) - 115907(25) PROFILE P1 FL230 → 50'

115944(28) - 121459(35) RUN 1 250'

125302(36) - 130001(41) RUN 2 250'

130502(42) - 134510(60) PROFILE P2 50' → FL260

025°

1033mb

1030mb

1030mb

141726

LAND Boscombe Darn

Mobile Phone

↳ 0374 192965

MRF 05 — Open University Methane Profile Experiment

Location: North Sea gas fields 54N2E and 52.5N2E

Meteorological Conditions: Stable conditions avoiding cloud where possible.

Flight Patterns: 1. Transit from Boscombe Down to operational area as convenient.

2. Execute clean air profile descent from 10,000 feet to minimum safe altitude (50 feet).

3. Straight and level runs at approx 250 ft to sample air upwind of gas field. ^{AMSL}

4. Straight and level runs at approx 250 ft to sample air downwind of gas field.

5. Execute polluted air profile ascent from minimum safe altitude (50 feet) to maximum altitude.

6. Return to Boscombe Down as convenient.

3 hrs 40

6:45 am Andrew departs

7:00 am Van cleavers depart

7:15 am crew depart

8:00 am On meet Andrew at main gate

8:30 am air crew brief

10:30 am take off if possible

A440 1 MARCH 1996
Aircraft Scientist Debrief.

open w methane profile.

- High Pressure to ~~west~~^{west} of U.K. frontal system down east coast.

- Sortie was less successful than hoped because far more cloud was encountered south of the oil rigs than initially anticipated. More loop used to make flight decisions was yesterday. Bottles we collected on the descent in clean air and samples up and downwind of oil rigs. although very solid cloud on profile out, a good set of bottles & bags were collected.

Pending analysis a good set of data was collected.

A440 01-MAR-96 11:00:00-14:00:00GMT

A440 01-MAR-96 Height time series

TRAJ_OUA0301.TXT

From 12Z 27/ 2/1996 to 12Z 1/ 3/1996

Arrows every 12 hrs

Plotted 15-Mar-1996 08:07

A440 Profile 2

temperature deiced temperature dew point total water dew point

A440 Profile 1

| temperature | deiced temperature | dew point | total water dew poin

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: OUME Date: 1/3/96
Flight No: A440 Page 1 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:52:15	12	TRANS	F100	P	?	?	?	A/c scientist Display Dead. —	
10:57:56		TRANS	F16	P	?	?	?	Clear above — no short contrail solid sc below. →	
11:04:45	4	TRANS	22700	P				Clear above solid sc below.	
11:07:13		TRANS	22900	P	?	?	?	some high cloud ahead broken sc below ahead solid Below.	
11:11:10		TRANS	22800	P	?	?	?	Clear below broken sc some cloud above.	
11:19:05		TRANS	22800	P	?	?	?	Streets of sc. clear above. messy ahead.	
11:23:05		TRANS	22800	P	?	?	?	solid sc. below request decent through Gap in cloud just of Yorkshire coast.	
11:24:52		P1	22800	P	315	—	—	Start of Profile P1.	
11:29:32	16	P1	18000	P	315	—	—	interp P1, Broken sc below lenticular streets clear above	
11:31:08	17	P1	18000	P	315	—	—	restart profile heading for. gap in sc. ahead.	
11:34:04		P1	14700	P	125	—	—	Broken sc below puffier to the east.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kanya

Project: OUME Date: 1/3/96
Flight No: A440 Page 2 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:36:15								Below Sc. dec sc. below.	
11:36:38		P1 P1	12000					interrupt P1 reciprocal turn for next leg of profile.	
11:39:18		P1	12000		319			Restart profile heading north.	
11:47:50		P1	5000		330	/		whitby. - broken sc above & below.	
11:52:30			4800						
11:54:50		P1	1500					sc above clear below. change profile route	
11:55:45		P1	1500		80			sc above hazy below.	
11:59:07		P1 P1	50	R	80	/		hazy sc above 3.3 pressure sea state b.	
11:59:43		R1	250					4 bottles & 11C bottles & bags to be filled.	
								Run interrupted by rain. heading back into reciprocal	
12:09:25		R1	250		270			sc above hazy.	
12:14:58		R1	250					end of run gaps ahead clear sc above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A Kaye

Project: OUME Date: 1/3/96
 Flight No: A440 Page 3 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:47:35			1700		/			Rain on windows <u>Solid cloud</u>	
12:54:30								40/12 some to 0.5mm -	
13:30:00									
13 ⁰⁸ 02								Rain hazy. 30 55-6	
								Bottles to fill @ 50, 1000, 2000, 3000, 4000, 5000 700 750 , 10000, <u>12500</u> , 15000 <u>17500</u> <u>2000</u> 22 24 26.	
13:21:57			8800					nearing cloud top.	
13:46:45			11300					sc below and above...	
13:30:00			13000					icing on wiper blades in cloud.	
13:30:38			13800					out of cloud <u>sc</u> solid sc below clear above one jet with contrail.	
13:34:17			15000					change of climb rate to 1800/min	
13:36:50			18000					sc below band band of a ahead at this height	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: OUME Date: 11/3/96

Flight No: A440 Page 4 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:41:09		P2	22300		290	-	-	(22) (24) E 26 K to be filled. 7/8 sc sc below - crystal clear above.	
13:44:58		P2	26000		290	-	-	7/8 sc below.	
13:47:48		P2	26000					end of science.	

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERC

Date: 11/3/96

User: *doxs*

Flight No: A440

Page 1 of 1

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
10:41	TRW806	8000'	25	1 ppm	meninglow = 96.9 (214 ps) - 24 ps/s E214 flow: 16.3 sample press = 101.3 mb
11:06	" "	28000'	54	" "	Adjusted torque on bleed valve, was too loose! flow = 97.1 e flow = 16.40
11:34	P1	14800	52 ppb	" "	Adjustment on Press. Bypass fully open
11:42	P1	9400	50.13	" "	Plane pressurized
11:58	P1	15000		" "	detector pressure 1081 at detector Press = 1134 e flow = 16.40 s flow = 97.1
13:09	P2	FL 188	54.04		Ozone very steady
13:39	P2	FL 200	58.92		pressing flow 2000'
13:46	P2	FL 260	58.90		end P2

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 4440

Date 1/3/96

Sheet no. 1 of 1

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	Control box			Full Tank pressure (mb)	Remarks
					Pump Pumping	Full Tank	Battery		
1	R9			250 ft	12:00:00	1201	120150	7hr	clear air
2	R11			250 ft	120250	120440	120540	"	250 ft
3	R38			"	120550	120850	120940	"	
4	R65			"	121049	12300	12355	"	
									Polluted? Air
5	R16			500 ft	124420	125325	125416	"	
6	R1			"	125514	125643	125738	"	
7	R20			"	125816	12598	130004	"	
8	R42			Around 500 ft	130254	130354	130438	"	

BAG Fillers Log	Flight No	Date	Operator
	A440	1/03/96	D.A.F

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
120000	101		250ft	1	FILLED 3 BAGS TO ONE
0100	102				BOTTLE
0130	3				
230	4				
300	5				
330	6				
500	8				
540	9				
605 ^F	10				
745	1				Run Inter 1207.
930	2				
950	3				
1130	4				
1145	5				
1210	6				
1330	7				
1400	8				
1430	9				
1500	20		↓	↓	
5340	1		500ft	2	FILLED 2 BAGS TO ONE
5405	2				BOTTLE
5510	3				
5535	4				
5720	5			↓	

213

BAG Fillers Log	Flight No	Date	Operator
	17440	1/03/96	D.A.F.

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
57 25	1 2 6		500ft	2	
69 00	7		↓		
59 18	8		↓		
1305 30	9		1	P2	
07 20	3 0				
09 15	3 1				
11 25	2				
13 50	3				
15 20	4				
16 05	5				
17 15	6				
19 40	7				
20 40	8				
25 15	9				
26 16	140				
29 43	41				
30 40	2				
31 40	3				
34 42	4				
35 25	5				
37 20	6				
39 25	7				
41 30	8				
43 45	9				SSS ₂ Fil.

DATE _____ TI MRF 05

1449 NAV HEATON

AIRFIELD BOSCOMBE

AIRFIELD Bore C1031
2009
1019

R/W 23 W/V 320/10 TEMP QNH 6035 OFF 6021

R/W 23 W/V 360/11 TEMP 46 1033 2009 1019 OFF 6103

WX CH 200

WX with 20K 8+2200 3000' S.

ATC CL 760. AFTER RETURN BACK ONA

ATC CL B2/KIN

T/O TIME

LAND TIME Hourly 1026. Spun 6025

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1105	013			210	299	355/67	F230	1013	N52500 W00239.0	MET
112453	311			180		350/70	F2230	1013	N54000 W000140.	P1 ↓
112931						350/66	F180	✓	N54087 W000070	INT P1
113109	131			180	225	350/60	F180 ↓	✓	N54099 W000020	RES P1 ↓
113633	121						F170	✓	N5353.1 E00026.0	INT P1
113920	315			180	211	348/67	F120	✓	N53540 E00022.0	RES INT P1
114630							F220		NOW 500 FPM	
115449						350/32	1500'		N54248 W000259	INT P1
115542074						345/32	11200'		N54257 W000229	RES P1
115907075				180		316/26	50'		N54270 W000070	END P1
115942075				180		317/23	250'		N5427.3 W0001.1	STR 1
120757				180		325/32	✓		N54311 E000420	END P1
120922180				180		335/26	250	ANN	N5429.6 E00037.0	RES R1
121451									N54300 E000100	END R1
125300				180		333/28	250'		N52387 E002203	STR 2
13000053				180		348/27	✓		N52514 E002234	END R2
130502				180		343/20	50'	500 FPM MAINT	N52490 E00239.4	STR 2
4510280				180		340/6	F260		N53129 W000320	END P2
									CLR & 6560 SE.	

INSTRUMENT STATUS AND REQUIREMENT FORM
A440 01MAR96 MRF

STANDARD INSTRUMENTS			NAVIGATION/AIRCRAFT PERFORMANCE		
EXP PIT STAT HEAD			INS	On	Ess
Static	On	Ess	GPS	On	Ess
Pitot-static	On	Ess	Mag compass	On	Ess
Wind Vanes	On	Des	Omega	On	Ess
			radar Alt	On	Ess
THERMOMETERS			CLOUD PHYSICS		
ICTP	On	Des	2D PRECIP	X	
De-iced	On	Ess	PCASP	On	Ess
Non De-iced	On	Ess	2D CLOUD	On	Des
HYGROMETERS			FSSP	On	Des
Gen East (1011)	On	Ess	HVPS	X	
Fluor W V S	On	Des	Holography	X	
Manual Hygro	X		JW	On	Des
			Tot Water	On	Des
AEROSOL SAMPLING			DROPSONDE SYSTEM		
Alleviator	X		Sondes	X	
Pollak	X		Receivers	On	
CCN	On		RADIOMETERS		
Nephelometer	On		BROAD BAND LOWER		
Filter boom	On		Standard Fit	On	Des
			Non standard	X	
CHEMICAL			BROAD BAND UPPER		
Bendix Ozone (eth)	On		Standard fit	On	Des
Desibi Ozone	X		Non standard	X	
Water Sampling	X		Obscurers (L)	X	
ECGC's	X		Obscurers (S)	On	
UEA Peroxide	X		NARROW BAND		
KFA	X		Barnes Prt4	On	Ess
			Marss	X	
IMAGERY			MCR/SAFIRE	X	
Weather Radar	X		<i>Bag fillins</i>		
Video Cameras	On	Des	<i>bottle fillins</i>		
Video Rec	On	Des			
Photo Cameras	On	Des			
Hand Held Video	On	Des			
DATA RECORDING					
CERL chart rec	X				
Video printer	On				
Horace	On	Ess			
DRS	On	Ess			

R : Remove, C : Cover
T/O TIME - 10:30 local

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ 	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log <i>OZONE, BAR FLUID, BOTTLE FILLER</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 	Particulate / Filter beam Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log ✓ Photographic log (photocopy original)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track